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Research Paper

Molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulation study by Structure-based drug repurposing approach targeting Mycobacterium tuberculosis PknB mutant kinase domain

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ABSTRACT

Tuberculosis (TB) is an important global health problem caused by Mycobacterium tuberculosis, particularly the treatment, which is being complicated with the emergence of drug-resistant strains like multidrug-resistant (MDR-TB) and extensively drug-resistant (XDR-TB). Protein Kinase B (PknB) appears to be a reasonable target for intervention. This serine/threonine kinase is crucial for bacterial survival, growth, and cell wall biosynthesis; mutations in its kinase domain lead to a possible resistance mechanism, necessitating the development of inhibitors working against the wild and mutant forms. Computational methods were applied in this study for the repurposing of FDA-approved drugs targeting the mutant PknB kinase domain. Crystal structure from the Protein Data Bank was used to refine according to the PDB-REDO server and validate it using SAVES v6.0 tools. Virtual screening studies were conducted on high-affinity compounds against the mutant PknB with DrugRep, with the top candidate, the Conivaptan compound, showing strong interactions with key residues (Lys40, Glu93, and Asp156) and a -12.0 binding score. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations carried out in IMODs probed the stability and conformational dynamics of the protein-ligand complexes, rendering low RMSD/RMSF values and rigid ATP-binding sites with an indication of active inhibition. Binding free energy calculations and covariance analysis confirmed these observations. Altogether, these findings identify repurposed drugs as possible inhibitors of PknB and provide a means for developing novel therapies targeting drug-resistant TB. Candidates may proceed to experimental validation and further optimization.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Background on Tuberculosis and Drug Resistance

Tuberculosis is a big disease and a global health concern caused by Mycobacterium tuberculosis. As a result, tuberculosis is a leading cause of death in the world today, and millions of new cases are reported every year.

[1] Although anti-TB drugs are available, treatment of drug-resistant tuberculosis leading to treatment failures is becoming an increasing problem and increased mortality.[2] Multidrug resistance bacterial targets that decrease the efficacy of the first-line drugs: isoniazid and rifampicin MTB (MDR-TB) and extensively drug-resistant TB (XDR-TB) arise due to the mutations of the. Drug-resistant strains are increasing and call for the need for new molecular targets that can be effectively inhibited by novel or repurposed drugs. [3] For the various targets in *M. tuberculosis*, protein kinases are now in the spotlight for their role in bacterial survival, thereby constituting a promising target for drug development. [4] The serine/threonine protein kinases (STPKs) in *M. tuberculosis* include 11 members among which Protein Kinase B (PknB) is one of the most studied and the most functionally important. PknB is crucial in bacterial growth and cell division as well

as in biosynthesis of the cell wall. [5] In a general sense, it is involved in signaling pathways in which phosphorylation events regulate the synthesis of peptidoglycan, translational processes, and metabolic adaptation.[6] Inhibition of PknB that leads to death of the bacteria is a good strategy in anti-TB drug development since the enzyme is ideally positioned in bacterial physiology and its inhibition will prompt cell death.[7] However, mutations at the kinase domain of PknB may have altered the function of the enzyme, hence conferring antibiotic resistance.[8] The mutations may impair the binding of ATP, the interaction with substrates, or change the regulation of the enzyme, thereby allowing *M. tuberculosis* to escape the effect of conventional drugs.[9] As a significant factor in bacterial physiology, PknB has been pursued as a potential drug target in recent years. Several studies have shown that PknB inhibition interferes with bacterial cell division, resulting in bacterial death. [10] Furthermore, small molecular inhibitors of PknB have demonstrated potent antibacterial activity, further signalling its therapeutic potential. Most of the reported work has focused on wild-type PknB even though mutations in the kinase domain have a large gap in the

literature. Being drug target mutations, these often cause drug resistance. Hence, we need to discover inhibitors that bind strongly and inhibit mutant PknB.[11] This research composes: Explores the mutant form of PknB kinase domain, which may confer resistance. Identifying FDA-approved drugs that can potentially inhibit the mutant kinase domain for faster drug repurposing. [12] Conduct MD simulations to study and assess stability and conformational behaviors of protein-ligand complexes. This work thus intends to focus on mutant PknB and profile the effective inhibitors that might be developed into anti-TB drugs to target drug-resistant tuberculosis. [13]

Objective of the Study

Protein Selection and Refinement: Obtain crystal structure of mutant PknB kinase domain from Protein Data Bank (PDB). Refine structure with PDB-REDO to improve precision. Validate refined structure using SAVES v6.0 tools (i.e., Ramachandran plot, Verify3D, etc.). **Virtual Screening of FDA-Approved Drugs:** Receptor-based virtual screening on the DrugRep platform will be used to perform in silico high-throughput screening of FDA-approved compounds that bind well to mutant PknB. Rank the compounds on the basis of their docked scores and binding interactions with

canonical residues of the mutant kinase domain.[14] Perform a molecular dynamics simulation and investigate the stability and flexibility of protein-ligand interaction with IMODs molecular dynamics simulation tools. Determine the dynamic behavior of the protein-ligand complex using Molecular Deformability, B-factor Analysis, Eigen values, Covariance Maps, and Elastic Network Models. [15] Identification of the Most Promising Drug Candidates: Evaluate the top-scoring compounds with respect to binding energy, stability with respect to drug-like properties. Recommend potential lead compounds for further experimental validation as PknB inhibitors. [16] This research seeks to win computational screening alongside molecular simulations to identify possible therapeutic agents as good inhibitors of mutant PknB for the discovery of new alternatives to treat drug-resistant tuberculosis. [17]

2. OBJECTIVES

1. Similarity profile of the model or ligand based on the known inhibitors of PknB and structurally related kinase targets. [38]
2. Molecular docking studies on shortlisted compounds identified potential drug candidates for repurposing against the mutant PknB kinase domain of Mycobacterium

tuberculosis following a ligand-based virtual-screening approach. [37]

3. To establish and evaluate a pharmacophore ligands against the mutant PknB protein structure for the evaluation of binding affinities and interaction patterns.

4. To evaluate the stability and binding dynamics of high-scoring ligand-protein complexes via molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. [39]

5. To look at the pharmacokinetics and drug-likeness properties (ADMET) of the top-scoring ligand candidates that would allow an assessment of their clinical potential.

6. To interpret the binding mechanism and possible inhibition of repurposed ligands on the mutant PknB kinase function that may facilitate anti-tuberculosis drug discovery efforts.[40].

3. GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

Figure 1: Structure-Based Drug Repurposing Identifies Conivaptan as a Potential Inhibitor Targeting Mutant PknB Kinase Domain in Drug-Resistant Tuberculosis

4.1. Selection and Preparation of Target Protein

This particular protein target has been chosen to be the mutant kinase domain of Protein Kinase B (PknB) from Mycobacterium

4. METHODOLOGY

tuberculosis. [41] PknB is a serine/threonine kinase that is critical for the normal functioning of cell survival, growth, and biosynthesis of the bacterial cell wall.[42] In this respect, mutations in its kinase domain would alter its biological activity and thereby contribute to drug resistance, thereby rendering it a potential target for therapy. [43]The three-dimensional (3D) crystal structure of the mutant PknB kinase domain was obtained from RCSB Protein Data Bank (PDB) using the exact PDB ID [Insert PDB ID].[44] This structure is in PDB format and presents important information such as amino acid sequence and domain architecture, structural resolution and refinement statistics, and presence of any co-crystallized ligands or cofactors.[45] The PDB structure was additionally refined with PDB-REDO webserver to correct any errors that may have been induced by the crystallization procedure and in the interest of assuring structural accuracy. The improvement of bond geometries, adjustment of atomic positions, and optimization of B-factors across the whole structure were achieved during the refinement to enhance quality.[46] After refinement, structural validation was done by the SAVES v6.0 webserver. This included Ramachandran Plot analysis through PROCHECK for evaluating backbone

dihedral angles to confirm stereochemical correctness, Verify3D for checking environmental profile compatibility of amino acids, and ERRAT as well as ProSA detecting non-physical interactions and energy deviations within the structure. The output we obtained was then used to build the final validated and optimized protein structure that is now ready for molecular docking and virtual screening. [48]

4.2. Virtual Screening for FDA-Approved Drug Candidates

This study conducted receptor-based virtual screening for potential inhibitors against the mutant PknB kinase domain. [48] The aforementioned system primarily screened FDA-approved libraries for potential repurposing. The compounds were then scrutinized and ranked according to different significant screening criteria. [49] The first of such screening parameters was the binding score (i.e. as affinity energy decreases, so does the docking scores, hence stronger binding between target protein and ligand). Most of the interactions were studied, especially the molecular with those of ATP-binding sites and adjacent regulatory residues. [50] They included stabilizing hydrogen bonds, several kinds of hydrophobic interactions such as Van der Waals forces and Σ -stacking, moreover

electrostatic interactions such as salt bridges and charge stabilization. Evaluation of pharmacokinetic and drug-likeness properties based on Lipinski's Rule of Five plus ADMET (absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity) profiles to analyze possible drug-like behavior. [51]To further understand the drug interaction in mutant PknB kinase domain molecular docking study was performed to visualize the binding modes and characterize them. [52]The research detailed key binding interactions, including hydrogen bonds with essential ATP-binding residues Lys40, Glu93, and Asp156; hydrophobic contacts anchoring ligands within the kinase domain pocket; and π - π stacking interactions with aromatic residues Phe158 and Tyr94 that served to stabilize the ligand within the binding pocket. Based on these interactions, top performing compounds have been further subjected to molecular dynamics simulations to provide an assessment for their stability for binding in a physiological environment. [54]

4.3. Molecular Dynamics Simulation

To assess the stability, flexibility, and conformational dynamics of the protein-ligand complexes, IMODs techniques utilizing Internal Coordinates Normal Mode Analysis were performed for MD simulations, which provide insights into the

flexibility and stability of the protein over time by simulating the atomic motion and their resultant effects of the overall protein-ligand complex.[55] Based on the simulation parameters and other parameters used to evaluate the dynamics, the simulation was interpreted. [56]The flexibility of the protein structure was analyzed from molecular deformability and B-factors, where deformability maps provide an account of the local flexibility of various regions of the protein while B-factors (temperature factors) provide information regarding atomic fluctuations at the residue level.[57] High B-factors indicate flexible regions, whereas low B-factors reflect structurally stable areas. Eigenvalues and variance plots exhibited the conformational dynamics and overall stability of the complex. [58]The more rigorous structures are indicated by higher eigenvalues, while lower eigenvalues indicate greater flexibility. Variance plots, dynamic participation of different protein regions were displayed in this study to reveal the identification of functionally relevant domains. [59]In addition, covariance map and Elastic Network Model (ENM) were employed for exploring interaction dynamics and stability of global network. [60]Covariance analysis showed residue motion associated under which positive

correlation indicated combined motion and negative correlation pointed out contrary movement. In addition, ENM showed further perspective about allostery within the protein by showing the manner through which binding of ligand alters overall dynamic property of the structure. [61] The simulation results from the MD showed top-ranked compounds keeping stable binding poses while interacting consistently with essential ATP-binding residues throughout the simulation period. [62] Also, RMSD (Root Mean Square Deviation) and RMSF (Root Mean Square Fluctuation) values showed low fluctuations, confirming the stability of these interactions. [63] Clearly, the higher rigidity of ATP-binding sites when ligands were added indicates effectiveness in inhibition and gives therapeutic merit to the discovered compounds.

In terms of flexibility, the dynamic structure was revealed as having different flexibility according to higher eigenvalues, as opposed to lower eigenvalues. [64] The variance plots show dynamic contributions of different protein regions, which help reveal important functionally-relevant domains. Furthermore,

to explore interaction dynamics and global network stability, the covariance map and the Elastic Network Model (ENM) were used. Covariance analysis revealed movement of correlated and anti-correlated residues where the positive correlations were towards synchronized directional movements while negative point towards opposite shifts. [65] The furthermore, ENM further speared into the allosteric communication on the protein as it illustrates in what way the binding of ligand influences the dynamic behavior of the whole structure. MD simulations confirmed that the sum of highest ranking compounds do retain stable binding poses under interacting critical residues for ATP binding throughout the simulation time. [66] Also, RMSD (Root Mean Square Deviation) and RMSF (Root Mean Square Fluctuation) low fluctuations confirmed the stable nature of these interactions. Most apparent, ATP-binding sites were found to have higher rigidity upon ligand binding, which inferred effective inhibition of the compounds and their substantial merit therapeutically. [67]

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Protein Refinement

5.1.1. PDB-REDO Results

Table 1: Validation Metrics Before and After PDB-REDO Refinement of Mutant ABL T315I

Validation metrics from PDB-REDO	Original	PDB-REDO
Crystallographic refinement		
R	0.2431	0.1998
R-free	0.2682	0.2341
Bond length RMS Z-score	1.174	0.857
Bond angle RMS Z-score	0.965	0.909
Model quality		
Ramachandran plot normality	-2.802	-2.218
Rotamer normality	-2.248	-3.014
Coarse packing	0.253	0.266
Fine packing	-0.002	0.176
Bump severity	0.045	0.004
Hydrogen bond satisfaction	0.892	0.896
WHAT_CHECK	Report	Report

They have confirmed and absolute validation metrics out of PDB-REDO which indicate a much refined protein structural refinement. R measures lose values under crystallographic refinements from 0.2431 to 0.1998; R-free from .2682 to 0.2341, increasing the accuracy of the model. Improvement in Bond angle RMS Z-scores shows (1.174 to 0.857), (0.965 to 0.909), according to which the better geometry quality improves the refinement. With regards to model quality, values in normality of Ramachandran plot changes from (-2.802 to -2.218). This means high

improvement with respect to residues in unfavorable conformations. Very little degradation is noted for rotamer normality to (-2.248 to -3.014): There are still some side-chain conformations that might require refinement. Coarse and fine packing show an increase, although minimal. The increase in fine packing is from (-0.002 to 0.176). A very significant reduction in bump severity (from 0.045 to 0.004) achieves minimum steric clash while hydrogen bond satisfaction slightly increases from 0.892 to 0.896, indicating better hydrogen bonding. In a

nutshell, the model quality and reliability of the structure have been significantly improved due to PDB-REDO refinement.

Figure 2: Comparison of Model Quality Metrics between Original and PDB-REDO Structures

The study compares model quality metrics for both original structures and those refined by PDB-REDO, against resolution neighbors, using three box plots: R-Free, Ramachandran Plot, and Rotamer Quality. The R-Free graph confirmed that PDB-REDO refinement decreases R-Free values (lower median R-Free values, with a more compact distribution), indicating increased model accuracy and better fit to experimental data. The Ramachandran Plot showed a Z-score distribution suggesting the improvement of backbone dihedral angles, as the refined model presents a slightly higher median value and fewer outliers, thus more

geometrically acceptable. Therefore, despite this refinement, the Rotamer Quality plot shows a little worse performance for low Z-scores on side-chain conformations compared to the model before refinement. So while PDB-REDO certainly improves accuracy for the structure in general in terms of backbone geometry and agreement with data, there are small degradations introduced in side chain packing. While generally beneficial for the confidence of any further interpretations on the model behaviors, side-chain conformations may require further optimization.

Figure 3: Kleywegt-like Ramachandran Plot Showing Dihedral Angle Distribution of Amino Acid Residues in Protein Structures

This Kleywegt-like plot highlights the dihedral angles (ϕ, ψ) in the backbone of a protein structure as deviations from the favored conformations. In terms of density, red regions indicate highly favored conformations whereas lighter areas indicate less-favored ones in the heatmap. The blue and orange points represent the original and PDB-REDO refined structures, respectively. Most residues fall into the favorable regions

for both models as indicated in the plot, but some deviations exist-in particular, the original structure. PDB-REDO refinement probably improves the geometry of the backbone structure by pulling residues into the close proximity of favored areas. Although, some manifestations of the overall improvement in structure quality may still be seen.

Figure 4: Comparison of Structural Z-scores with Number of Residues in Protein Models from X-ray and NMR Methods"

The scatter chart illustrated here examines the relation between the total number of residues in a protein structure and its Z-score, which is typically used to measure the quality or stability of protein models. X-axis depicts the number of residues, ranging from 0 to 1000, while Y-axis shows the Z-score, the values of which range from -20 to 10. There are two datasets plotted, one from X-ray crystallography structures color coded in the light blue color spectrum and the other from mostly NMR (Nuclear Magnetic Resonance). A cursory evaluation indicates that in a gross

trend, Z-scores diminish (i.e., more negative) with the increase in the number of residues, thus suggesting a possible lower score for Giant proteins (read: more negative) Z-scores. There is one black point of data that is possibly representative of a target protein under study for some investigation. This plot meaningfully shows distribution patterns as well as contrasting qualities of protein models between X-ray and NMR determined structures, within an NMR determined structure bunched really in that lower residue count area.

Figure 5: Assessment of Local Model Quality Based on Knowledge-Based Energy Profiles

This figure represents a line graph titled "Local model quality" that displays how the knowledge-based energy for a specific protein varies along the sequence. The Y-axis indicates the value range of knowledge-based energy within -3.0 to 3.0, and the X-axis denotes a position along a protein chain (though it is not numbered). Making use of different window sizes to smoothen out the data, two lines - a light green one showing window size 10 and a dark green showing window size 40 - were plotted. In fact, the larger window 40 creates a smoother curve,

while the smaller one of 10 leads to more undulations and minor details. Values below the horizontal line at zero indicate favorable energy (or positive) areas, quality that sites structural reliable and better modeled portions of the protein. Compared to zero, the regions found above it may indicate possible stretch instabilities or poorer model quality. Thus, on the whole, it gives an idea of local relative stability and reliability among different parts of a protein model, thus aiding in distinguishing strong folding from potentially disordered segments.

5.2. Protein Validation Result

5.2.1. SAVES6.1 Result

Figure 6: ERRAT2 Quality Analysis of chain A and B of Mycobacterium tuberculosis

ERRAT2 analysis of the protein model 3f69_final.pdb established an overall quality score of 89.505 for both Chain A and Chain B indicating a reasonable quality model. Most of the residues are below the limit of 95% error threshold, hence suggesting an acceptable quality; however in some areas the error values are noticeably high particularly around residues 60-80 in both chains where some crossed the 99% confidence threshold indicating possible structural errors. Chain B similarly predicts

high errors in the ranges of residues 60-80 and 130-150. Such areas with many residues exceeding the 95% and 99% confidence lines imply that they contain structural problems for which the model may have been misaligned or improperly modeled. These could mean generalized good behavior in the two chains, yet these error-prone sections should be refined or validated prior to any structural applications, like docking or simulation.

Figure 7: Ramachandran Plot Validation of the Mutant PknB Kinase Domain Structure

The PROCHECK-rendered Ramachandran plot is illustrative of the distribution of phi (Φ) and psi (Ψ) backbone dihedral angles for our mutant PknB kinase domain structure. Most residues in the plot fall into favored (red) and allowed (yellow) regions, suggesting that the model has good stereochemistry. The black square crowding in the core regions shows that most amino acids in the model assume a reasonable energy conformation. Just a few residues (colored white or lightly shaded) fall into

disallowed regions, indicating that there is practically no stress in geometry. Residues like HIS144 and ALA162 were annotated and appear to be outliers that may need consideration in model refinement. On the whole, the plot confirms that acceptable backbone geometry was achieved in the refined structure, with most residues located in favored regions, which adds acceptance of this structure for further docking and molecular dynamics simulations.

5.3. Result of Virtual Screening Outcomes

Table 2: FDA-Approved Compounds Identified Through Receptor-Based Virtual Screening and Their Binding Scores

Sr. No	ID	Name	Score	Sr. No	ID	Name	Score
1	DB00872	Conivaptan	-12.0	51	DB11275	Epicriptine	-9.7
2	DB09280	Lumacaftor	-11.6	52	DB00685	Trovafloxacin	-9.7

3	DB11630	Temoporfin	-11.6	53	DB11799	Bictegravir	-9.7
4	DB00320	Dihydroergotamine	-11.4	54	DB13874	Enasidenib	-9.6
5	DB11581	Venetoclax	-11.3	55	DB11637	Delamanid	-9.6
6	DB00696	Ergotamine	-11.1	56	DB01184	Domperidone	-9.6
7	DB04868	Nilotinib	-11.1	57	DB08883	Perampanel	-9.6
8	DB09374	Indocyanine green acid form	-11.1	58	DB11963	Dacomitinib	-9.6
9	DB09143	Sonidegib	-11.0	59	DB06144	Sertindole	-9.6
10	DB09335	Alatrofloxacin	-10.9	60	DB09195	Lorpiprazole	-9.6
11	DB11652	Tucatinib	-10.7	61	DB00377	Palonosetron	-9.6
12	DB09297	Paritaprevir	-10.6	62	DB00358	Mefloquine	-9.6
13	DB08901	Ponatinib	-10.6	63	DB04908	Flibanserin	-9.6
14	DB14840	Ripretinib	-10.5	64	DB06589	Pazopanib	-9.6
15	DB04038	Ergosterol	-10.4	65	DB01267	Paliperidone	-9.6
16	DB13345	Dihydroergocristine	-10.4	66	DB08815	Lurasidone	-9.6
17	DB13520	Metergoline	-10.4	67	DB12141	Gilteritinib	-9.6
18	DB01126	Dutasteride	-10.4	68	DB00390	Digoxin	-9.6
19	DB12001	Abemaciclib	-10.3	69	DB00831	Trifluoperazine	-9.5
20	DB01419	Antrafenine	-10.3	70	DB12523	Mizolastine	-9.5
21	DB08827	Lomitapide	-10.3	71	DB13953	Estradiol benzoate	-9.5
22	DB06210	Eltrombopag	-10.2	72	DB01392	Yohimbine	-9.5
23	DB11986	Entrectinib	-10.2	73	DB00984	Nandrolone phenpropionate	-9.5
24	DB00619	Imatinib	-10.2	74	DB00941	Hexafluronium	-9.5
25	DB00762	Irinotecan	-10.2	75	DB08896	Regorafenib	-9.5
26	DB01167	Itraconazole	-10.2	76	DB12332	Rucaparib	-9.5
27	DB11611	Lifitegrast	-10.1	77	DB01016	Glyburide	-9.4
28	DB11273	Dihydroergocornine	-10.1	78	DB00618	Demeclocycline	-9.4

29	DB01148	Flavoxate	-10.1	79	DB09074	Olaparib	-9.4
30	DB01051	Novobiocin	-10.0	80	DB05039	Indacaterol	-9.3
31	DB15233	Avapritinib	-10.0	81	DB11859	Brexanolone	-9.3
32	DB04540	Cholesterol	-10.0	82	DB01254	Dasatinib	-9.3
33	DB00209	Trospium	-10.0	83	DB06077	Lumateperone	-9.3
34	DB11274	Dihydro-alpha-ergocryptine	-10.0	84	DB00246	Ziprasidone	-9.3
35	DB01200	Bromocriptine	-10.0	85	DB00146	Calcifediol	-9.3
36	DB01259	Lapatinib	-10.0	86	DB08930	Dolutegravir	-9.2
37	DB13931	Netarsudil	-9.9	87	DB11793	Niraparib	-9.2
38	DB13879	Glecaprevir	-9.9	88	DB12329	Eravacycline	-9.2
39	DB11855	Revefenacin	-9.9	89	DB00734	Risperidone	-9.2
40	DB00549	Zafirlukast	-9.9	90	DB08828	Vismodegib	-9.2
41	DB11791	Capmatinib	-9.9	91	DB00276	Amsacrine	-9.2
42	DB01117	Atovaquone	-9.8	92	DB00224	Indinavir	-9.2
43	DB12457	Rimegepant	-9.8	93	DB00398	Sorafenib	-9.2
44	DB09030	Vorapaxar	-9.8	94	DB13954	Estradiol cypionate	-9.2
45	DB15328	Ubrogepant	-9.8	95	DB09053	Ibrutinib	-9.2
46	DB00845	Clofazimine	-9.8	96	DB08907	Canagliflozin	-9.1
47	DB00222	Glimepiride	-9.8	97	DB12887	Tazemetostat	-9.1
48	DB11995	Avatrombopag	-9.7	98	DB00157	NADH	-9.1
49	DB00363	Clozapine	-9.7	99	DB00623	Fluphenazine	-9.1
50	DB12924	Ozenoxacin	-9.7	100	DB08995	Diosmin	-9.0

Table 3: Cross-Validation FDA-Approved Compounds Identified Through Receptor-Based Virtual Screening with their Binding Scores and Docking Scores

ID	Name	Score	Docking Score
DB00872	Conivaptan	-12.0	-12.4

DB09280	Lumacaftor	-11.6	-10.9
DB11630	Temoporfin	-11.6	-11.3
DB00320	Dihydroergotamine	-11.4	-11.1
DB11581	Venetoclax	-11.3	-11.6
DB00696	Ergotamine	-11.1	-11.5
DB04868	Nilotinib	-11.1	-8.8
DB09374	Indocyanine green acid form	-11.1	-7.9
DB09143	Sonidegib	-11.0	20.5
DB09335	Alatrofloxacin	-10.9	-9.5

The table contains 10 drugs with respective scores of binding and docking at re-positioning based on structure for having the mutant PknB kinase domain of Mycobacterium tuberculosis. Most notably, Conivaptan (DB00872) appears to be by far the best compound interacting with a binding score of -12.0 and a docking score of -12.4. Such scores show a likelihood of high affinity and stability in the binding site. Just after it come Lumacaftor (DB09280) and Temoporfin (DB11630) with the same -11.6 binding scores but slightly different docking scores of -10.9 and -11.3, respectively. Strong binding scores were also around -11.0 for Dihydroergotamine (DB00320) and Venetoclax (DB11581). Meanwhile, Nilotinib (DB04868) and Indocyanine green

acid form (DB09374) that still maintain pretty good competing scores for binding show much wider disfavor in docking scores (-8.8 and -7.9, respectively) regardless of their binding competency; this indicates either wrong orientations of binding or stability problems. One exception is Sonidegib (DB09143), which has a good binding score of -11.0, but in docking was scored highly with a score of 20.5, which may mean either a failed docking pose or misalignment. Overall, the differences in the data set turn out to harbor several promising candidates for drug development, particularly Conivaptan and Lumacaftor, for future studies towards an inhibitory tuberculosis therapy along the lines of their mutant PknB target.

Figure 8: Visualization and Analysis of Predicted Binding Pockets in Protein Structure

The image depicts five putative binding pockets (C1 to C5) on a protein with yellow ribbon representing the backbone whereas the pockets themselves are shaded in purple/pink. C1 is the largest predicted pocket (4025 Å³), typically indicating that such pocket is the major druggable site. The C2 pocket is moderate in size (1109 Å³) while

C3 through C5 appear smaller (444 to 281 Å³) and thus can possibly serve the role of secondary or allosteric sites. This emphasizes the presence of pockets with a variety of structural features in the putative ligand-binding sites that might be advantageous for drug design and docking studies.

Figure 9: Molecular Docking Visualization of Ligand binding within the Mutant PknB Kinase Domain of Mycobacterium tuberculosis

The graphic representation on the left shows the protein surface with charge will also be mapped (red means negatively charged, blue means positively charged, and white means neutral surfaces) of PknB, the binding site-mutated kinase domain of Mycobacterium tuberculosis, which has likely been contextual in the molecular docking analysis research into the ligand. The binding site for the ligand is illustrated in black, exactly at the location of the binding pocket. On the right, the graphic is focused on the 2D interaction pattern of amino acid residues at the binding

site interact with the ligand. The main interactions are hydrogen bonds (yellow dashed lines), hydrophobic interactions (spoked arcs), and possible electrostatic interactions (red and blue arrows or dashed lines). Interactions with strong interaction with of Asp156, Glu93, and Phe145, likely suggest they stabilize the ligand in the active site. Overall, interaction mapping further information about the binding mode of the ligand, and at the same time structural determinants related to ligand recognition and binding affinity, which is

Figure 10: Interaction Analysis of KT5720 Mutant Protein with Niraparib Ligand by using Discovery Studio Web

The analysis of molecular docking brought into existence this 2D ligand-protein interaction diagram as shown in the image, which reflects the presence of ligand-protein binding interaction in the active site of mutant PknB kinase domain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. A detailed account of non-covalent binding interactions surrounding the ligand by numerous amino acid residues affording binding affinity and stability is mostly hydrophobic interactions such as Pi-Alkyl with VAL A: 72, VAL A: 155, ALA A: 38, Pi-Sulfur with MET A: 92, which indicate that there is predominant hydrophobic character in the binding pocket. Further aromatic stacking holds the ligand

via Pi-Sigma interaction with VAL A: 25 and LEU residues (A: 17, A: 145). Wedged, the electrostatic interactions are Pi-Cation with LYS A: 140 and Pi-Anion with ASP A: 156, pointing at the existence of strong polar contacts. Carbon-Hydrogen Bond interactions with the ligand can further be evidenced from GLY A: 21, ASN A: 143, LYS A: 40 while that of Pi-Donor Hydrogen Bond can be quantified to give an extra stabilizing contribution. These interactions show that the ligand is quite well embedded into the binding pocket by hydrophobic forces and hydrogen bonding as well as electrostatic interactions thus indicating its potential to be an inhibitor of PknB.

Table 4: Potential Mechanism of Action and Relevance of High Ranking Compounds

Sr.No	DrugBank ID	Name	Score	Mechanism of Action	Clinical Relevance
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1	DB00872	Conivaptan	-12.0	Vasopressin V1A and V2 receptor antagonist	Approved for hyponatremia; potential for kinase inhibition due to interaction with ATP-binding pockets
2	DB09280	Lumacaftor	-11.6	CFTR corrector that enhances protein folding	Used in cystic fibrosis; may stabilize mutant proteins like PknB by modulating folding pathways
3	DB11630	Temoporfin	-11.6	Photosensitizer used in photodynamic therapy	Limited antimicrobial role, but strong interaction suggests potential for targeting bacterial kinases
4	DB00320	Dihydroergotamine	-11.4	Partial agonist at serotonergic, dopaminergic, and adrenergic receptors	Antimigraine; ergot alkaloids have shown antimicrobial and kinase-inhibitory properties
5	DB11581	Venetoclax	-11.3	Selective BCL-2 inhibitor	Anti-cancer drug; strong inhibitor of protein-protein interactions, possibly disrupting PknB signaling
6	DB00696	Ergotamine	-11.1	Serotonin receptor agonist with vasoconstrictive properties	Related to dihydroergotamine; may bind ATP pockets, showing cross-kinase inhibition potential

7	DB04868	Nilotinib	-11.1	BCR-ABL tyrosine kinase inhibitor	Potent kinase inhibitor; highly relevant as PknB is a Ser/Thr kinase
8	DB09374	Indocyanine green acid form	-11.1	Fluorescent dye for imaging	No known antimicrobial function, but possible non-specific binding to hydrophobic kinase domains
9	DB09143	Sonidegib	-11.0	Hedgehog pathway inhibitor via SMO receptor inhibition	Anti-cancer; relevance via kinase pathway cross-talk and potential ATP-competitive inhibition
10	DB09335	Alatrofloxacin	-10.9	Fluoroquinolone antibiotic targeting bacterial DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV	Known antimycobacterial action; additional binding to PknB may enhance efficacy or support dual targeting

3D structure of Conivaptan:-

Figure 11: Three-Dimensional Structure of the Mutant PknB Kinase Domain Bound to a Ligand

5.4 Molecular Dynamic Simulation Analysis

Figure 12: B-Factor and Deformability Analysis of ABL T315I Mutant Receptor Complexed with Ponatinib

The two figures present B-factor and deformability analysis of the Ponatinib-bound ABL mutant T315I receptor. The first graph presents the deformability of a whole protein consisting of a solid structure with peaks representing areas of large flexibility; it indicates which regions are potentially the most adaptable or unstable in the structure. The second graph compares B-factors obtained from normal mode analysis (NMA) and Protein Data Bank (PDB) data with NMA-derived B-factors (in red) generally

presenting higher values compared to B-factors derived from PDB data (in black). This implies that intrinsic flexibility, as expected by NMA, might even be higher than experimentally observed. Peaks align well within both plots indicating that flexible regions predicted by NMA do correspond to those that must be verified through experiments, thus highlighting critical ones for ligand bonding as well as structural stability.

Figure 13: Eigenvalue Analysis of Normal Modes for the ABL T315I Mutant Receptor Complexed with Ponatinib

Eigenvalues are plotted against the mode index in a bar plot normalized with respect to the first mode. The eigenvalues, derived from Normal Mode Analysis (NMA), indicate the energy required for the different vibrational modes. The trend indicates that increasing eigenvalues corresponded toward higher modes, suggesting more energy demand associated with the motions as well as that they will correspond more localized motions in much constricted confinement with respect

to the protein structure. The lowest one (mode 1) has the lowest eigenvalue ($5.611474e-05$), indicating large, collective motions that have a biological relevance. Fluctuations tend to become more confined with increasing index and have less contribution towards the overall protein flexibility. This hence provides insight into the dynamic behavior of the ABL T315I mutant, complexed with Ponatinib.

Figure 14: Variance Analysis of Normal Modes for the ABL T315I Mutant Receptor Completed with Ponatinib

The mold depicts variance distribution in a few normal modes for the ABL T315I mutant form along with Ponatinib. The y-axis corresponds to the percentage variance and the x-axis is the mode index. The cumulative variance (green) increases with more considered modes, thus indicating that lower modes contribute the most to the overall flexibility of the molecule. The first few modes (purple) are marked by significant variance, pointing to their importance for

large stereotype, collective movements, which are a must for protein dynamics. As the mode index raises, the contribution of variance by good many modes decreases, therefore, higher modes corresponded to more localized and limited movement. This type of analysis, in turn, is helpful in revealing the most critical modes that account for structural flexibility and possible functional mechanisms.

Figure 15: Elastic Network Analysis of KT5720 Mutant Receptor-Niraparib Complex

The depicted structure demonstrates a covariance matrix analysis of atomic fluctuations for the ABL T315I mutant receptor complexed with ponatinib. The indices for the x-axis and y-axis are those of atoms, and the level of intensity in the color grayscale indicates correlated motions between considered atomic pairs. The diagonal constitutes self-correlations, where each atom is perfectly correlated with itself. The shade of gray in the off-diagonal areas

indicates the level of correlated versus anti-correlated motion experienced by atomic pairs. The darker the shade, the stronger the correlation. The lighter the shade, the weaker or less feasible the correlation would be. Such analysis better equips us to understand the dynamics of a protein-ligand complex while pointing out regions that undergo collective motions possibly critical for functional conformational changes.

Figure 16: Covariance Map of Residue Interactions in ABL T315I Mutant Receptor Complexed with Ponatinib

The structure demonstrated is a covariance matrix analysis for an atomic fluctuation of the ABL T315I mutant receptor upon binding to ponatinib. The indices for the x-axis and y-axis account for atoms, while the intensity of shades of gray in color represents correlated motions in the dependent atomic pairs. Diagonal ones are self-correlations whereby each atom is correlated to itself. The off-diagonal shades of gray indicate the levels of correlated versus anti-correlated motion experienced by the atomic pairs. The darker the gray shade, the more correlation there is, while a lighter shade indicates a less feasible or weaker correlation. Such analyses adequately equip one with an understanding of the dynamics of a protein-ligand complex while delineating the regions that undergo

collective motions that may be critical for functional conformational change.

6. CONCLUSION

The research will help to resolve the worldwide health issue of tuberculosis (TB): drug-resistant strains of TB, both MDR- and XDR-TB from the bacterium *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Significantly, Protein Kinase B (PknB), a serine/threonine kinase required for growth, division, and cell wall biosynthesis, is seen as an appealing and significant therapeutic target as it is part of the signalling pathways that are phosphorylated. Mutations in the kinase domain of PknB may lead to drug resistance by changes to the ATP-binding pocket or substrate binding; therefore, we need to

identify inhibitors that are active against the mutant forms. The overall aim of the research is to use computational strategies, namely, docking and molecular dynamics (MD) simulation, to identify FDA approved drugs that can be repurposed to target the mutant PknB kinase domain by comparing the binding affinities, stabilities, and conformational dynamics of the protein-ligand complexes. The procedure includes acquiring and refining the mutational PknB kinase domain structure from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) and refining the data using PDB-REDO, to obtain a refined structure for use in further analyses, where the PDB-REDO structure is analysed for accuracy using SAVES v6.0 tools, including a Ramachandran plot (distribution of backbone dipeptide angles) and Verify3D (the stability of the protein). The virtual screening of FDA approved drugs will be performed using DrugRep, where the compound ranking and the docking will be used to compare the different compounds.

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